

Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from a boat found in Vordingborg, Denmark.

by
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Vordingborg Boat

Three samples from planks from a boat found at Vordingborg were selected for dendrochronological analysis, to determine their date and provenance. The results of this analysis are described in this report.

All three samples are of *Quercus sp.*, oak and all are dated.

Sample x1124

Sample x1124 is from a garboard. It contains 198 tree-rings, including 9 sapwood rings. The tree-ring curve from the sample covers the period AD 1154-1351. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree that the plank was made from is estimated at c. AD 1351-66 (see fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Vordingborg Boat. The chronological position of the dated samples.

Sample x1125

This sample is also from a garboard. It contains 245 tree-rings, all heartwood. This sample is dated. The tree-ring curve from the sample covers the period AD 1103-1347. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date of the tree that this plank was made from is estimated at after AD 1357 (fig. 1).

Sample x1071

Sample x1071 is from a plank that, in terms of the boat's construction, appears to be a repair or to have been later inserted. It contains 199 tree-rings, including 3 sapwood rings. The tree-ring curve from the sample covers the period AD 1151-1349. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree that this plank was made from is estimated at c. AD 1355-70 (see fig. 1).

			Z219001a	Z219002a	Z219003a
Average Z219M001	X1124	Z219001a	*	5,52	3,81
	X1071 rep	Z219002a	5,52	*	5,39
	X1125	Z219003a	3,81	5,39	*

Table 1. Vordingborg Boat. Result of the correlation between each dated sample with each other. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Considering the high agreement between the three planks (as shown in table 1) the results might indicate that the later inserted plank was placed during the building of the original boat. If this is taken to be the case then if we combine the dating estimates for the three individual planks, it can be suggested that the trees for the planks were felled between c. AD 1355 and 1366 (marked with green in fig. 1).

Filenames	-	-	Z219M001	
-	start	dates	AD 1103	
-	dates	end	AD 1351	
Master and site chronologies				
P671001m	AD 980	AD 1347	11.08	Poland Elblag (Wazny pers comm)
PM670108	AD 725	AD 1985	10.91	PL Gdansk (Wazny pers comm)
PP125M01	AD 917	AD 1400	9.56	PL Elblag 150 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
PP124M01	AD 982	AD 1356	9.18	PL Elblag 120 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
DM200005	AD 915	AD 1873	8.64	Niedersachsen Nord (Göttingen Uni)
DM200006	AD 914	AD 1873	8.43	Lüneburger Heide (Göttingen Uni)
PP114M01	AD 1152	AD 1447	8.29	PL Gdansk Wole 18 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
P676001m	AD 1084	AD 1393	7.96	Poland Kolobrzeg (Wazny pers comm)
G1101Z03	AD 1124	AD 1319	7.81	Flensburg 4 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
PP106M01	AD 1110	AD 1399	7.71	PL Gdansk Parc.6 14 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
G350PZ01	AD 967	AD 1381	7.32	Truhen 46 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
DM100010	AD 1023	AD 1723	7.29	Lübeck (Hamburg Uni)
0676001S	AD 1067	AD 1305	7.18	Kolobrzeg 7 timbers (Wazny pers comm)
Ships, boats and barrels				
Z0952M01	AD 1190	AD 1345	11.04	Barcode boat 17 BC17 Norway 2 timbers (Daly 2016a)
D0132M02	AD 1096	AD 1336	10.93	Thomas B Thriges barrel staves 7 timbers (Daly 2016b)
CLS2000	AD 1110	AD 1393	9.36	Hull Chapel Lane Yorkshire 11 boat planks (Tyers pers comm)
CD40UZ03	AD 1102	AD 1351	9.32	Brogade 2 timbers (Nationalmuseet revised Daly 2007)
HMC_T165	AD 1078	AD 1369	9.28	Hull boards from 37 coffins Yorkshire (Tyers pers comm)
Z005M003	AD 1063	AD 1373	8.88	Bølevraget Norway planks 4 timbers (Daly & Nymoer 2006)
0045M002	AD 1109	AD 1370	8.67	Vejby skib 18 trees (Bonde & Jensen 1995)
se617M01	AD 1100	AD 1396	8.52	New Baxtergate Grims 5 timbers (Sheffield Uni revised Daly 2007)
doel1_repai...	AD 1142	AD 1281	8.18	Ship timbers Doel 1_repair (Haneca & Daly 2014)
doel1_all_m2	AD 1150	AD 1305	7.72	Ship timbers Doel 1 (Haneca & Daly 2014)
0056M001	AD 1174	AD 1335	7.46	Aberdeen barrel (Crone pers comm)
02071M01	AD 1126	AD 1414	7.29	Dokøen Vrag 2 (Eriksen 2001)
P0011009	AD 1103	AD 1403	7.26	Copper Ship - wainscots (Wazny pers comm)

Table 2. Vordingborg Boat. Result of the correlation between the average curve for the dated samples (Z219M001) and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Provenance

The tree-ring curves from the planks cross-match with t -values as shown in table 1. Significant correlation is achieved between each plank with each other. In terms of the internal correlation, the repair plank fits very well with the two garboards. An average tree-ring curve of 249 years in length is calculated (Z219M001) from all three planks. This average covers the period AD 1103-1351. The correlation between this curve and a range of tree-ring datasets for oak for Northern Europe is shown in table 2. It is achieving highest correlation (t -values) with master and site chronologies for the region around the Gulf of Gdansk and with tree-ring data derived from archaeological finds of diverse other 14th century ships, boats and barrels that have been shown to also to be made from oaks from the Lower Vistula region.

Previous analysis

Four samples from this boat were analysed previously; from three planks and part of the keel (Eriksen 2012). The samples all contain relatively few tree-rings (from 40 to 69 rings). Eriksen reports two dated samples, and an estimated felling date for the trees used for the boat at after c. 1390 (no sapwood on the samples). Eriksen has very kindly shared his tree-ring data from these four samples with me. When I compare his data from the boat with Northern European tree-ring datasets for oak I find that correlations appear for many dating positions. This is due to the very short series that this material consists of. In light of the new analysis, where very long-lived trees from the boat are analysed and dated, producing very high and widely replicated correlations at the material's dating position, it might be prudent to revise the conclusions in the previous analysis, and consider these undated.

Methodology

Measuring and analysis of the material is carried out using the program "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) and for the calculation of the t -value (" t -test") "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is used. To estimate the felling dates of the trees a sapwood average for Northern Poland is used (15 years (-6 +9) (Wazny 1990)). In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are consulted.

Literature

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Catalogue

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
Z219001a	Vordingborg Båden VIR2812 x1124 garboard QUSP	198	AD 1154	AD 1351	G	9	N	R	N	1,11	AD 1351-66
Z219002a	Vordingborg båden VIR2812 x1071 repair plank QUSP	199	AD 1151	AD 1349	G	3	N	R	S1	1,16	AD 1355-70
Z219003a	Vordingborg båden VIR2812 x1125 plank QUSP	245	AD 1103	AD 1347	G	0	N	R	H1	0,89	after AD 1357
Averages											
Z219M001	Vordingborg Båden VIR2812 3 timbers QUSP	249	AD 1103	AD 1351						1,01	
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak. PISY = <i>Pinus sp.</i> , pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp/Larix sp.</i> , spruce/larch. ABAL = <i>Abies sp.</i> , fir.											
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